

Original Research

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ACHIEVERS JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH*Open Access Publications of Achievers University, Owo*Available Online at www.achieversjournalofscience.org**Communication Skill and Job Performance of Health Records Officer****Officers in Osun State Primary Health Care Board****¹Adebayo, T.T., ²Babagana, M., ¹Adejo, M.B., ³Adio, R.A., ⁴Akindele A.F., ⁵Omole, S.M. and ¹Omolara M.A.**¹Health Information Department, Achievers' University, Owo, **Ondo State.**²Health Officer Registration Board of Nigeria, Abuja.³Health Information Department, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nasarawa State.⁴Health Information Department, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo.⁵Health Information Department, College of Health Technology, Ilesa.Corresponding Author: Adebayo, T. T. adebayott@gmail.com

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Abstract

Every organization requires the effective utilization and management of effective communication and its related tools for the passing of important information and for improving workers' relationship with others. Good communication skill is one of the most important factors in creating an efficient work environment that promotes productivity and efficiency. Despite the importance of good communication skill, it was observed that this vital skill is missing in many health records professionals. Many of the professionals sometimes struggle to convey their thoughts and ideas in an accurate manner, making it difficult to reach their full potential, hence hindering their job performance. The main objective of this study is to assess the influence of Communication skills on Job Performance of Health Records Officers working in Osun State Primary Health Care Development Board. The study is cross-sectional research using Focused Group Discussion (FGD) guide to extract information from the Health Records Officers. Data were analyzed using Descriptive Statistics. The result of the study reveals that a relationship exists between good communication skills and job performance, productivity and commitment. Based on the findings, it was concluded that effective communication skills lead to good human relations, promotes Job performances and organization goal attainment. It was recommended that the Health Information Officers working in Osun State Primary Health Care Development Board should adopt good communication skills and strategies to enable them communicate effectively if they are to promote good relationship which will help them to demonstrate high job performance in their chosen career.

Keywords: Communication Skills; Health Records Officers; Influence; Job Performance

1. Introduction

All human intentions are a form of communication. In every standard setting, nothing can be achieved without effective communication skills. Several structures emphasized that communication skills enhanced full performance (Garnelt *et al.* 2008). Communication influences the perception and opinion about persons, communities, organization, government and even society. It is an indispensable tool frequently expected to share information with members, to coordinate activities, to reduce unnecessary management burden, roles ultimately to improve job performance (Euiju, 2009). Communication skills are adaptation skills that can modulate job stress. It is referred to as behavior which can help individual express their feelings and needs well in order to achieve their interpersonal goals.

Health Records Management is a profession that has multiple roles and each of these roles have general and specific duties. The most important duty of Health Records Officer is to maintain and promote individual and human society's health care through accurate, adequate and timely information. Health Information Practitioners "play crucial roles in the maintenance, collection and analyzing of data, which in turn assist greatly in the deliverance of quality health care" Adebayo (2019). Adebayo and Orimoloye (2019) also opined that Health information management practice is imperative in any health service providing institution in ensuring quality service delivery. In fact as put by Adebayo and Gbabee (2021), Health information management practice remains the cornerstone in supplying health care delivery system with a qualified and trained workforce to provide a quality services and specifically to provide high quality data

This becomes important as Adebayo and Omole (2019) put it "Building a healthy nation has become a herculean task due to the dearth of reliable data on the health status of the entire population". Everyone in the society needs information to function well because it is the underlying resources for sustainable economic, political, communal and social development (Adebayo & Omole; 2019). Adebayo (2019) believes everyone in the society needs information to function well because it is the underlying resources for sustainable economic, political, communal and social development. Also, establishing suitable communication among each other based on professional ethics. Skill communication is essential for Health Records Officer in order to maintain effective, sensitive relationship, to create room for improvement and consequently better performance. The importance of communication skill related to Health Records Officer is performance leads to this study, to evaluate the influence of communication skills on job performance of Health Records Officer in Osun State Primary Healthcare Development Board.

The quality of care is not an independent variable but it is the complex structure of values, beliefs, and attitude of people who are interacting together in the health care system. Health Records profession is more important among health care providers in health setting because it is an orbit in which all other healthcare services revolve. Hence providing adequate, accurate and timely information improve fueling care and services. Merkouris *et al.* (2004) described quality of information provided by Health Records Officer as enhancement to effective decision making. Good communication leads to skill acquisition and improvement in job performance. In order to establish reflective communication Health Records Officer should learn necessary skills for establishing a good relationship with one another.

Communication is the process of creating, transmitting, and interpreting ideas, facts, opinions and feelings. It is a process that is essentially a sharing one in a mutual interchange between two or more persons. Communication skills are critical to efficient job performance, professional achievement and organization success. Skills includes effective communication, problem solving, team building and listening, hence enhance standard job performance.

Communication has been widely accepted by scholars and academics as the life hood of an organization because communication is needed for exchanging information, exchanging opinions, making plans and proposals, reaching agreement, executing decisions, sending and fulfilling orders and conducting sales (Alyssa, 2006). When communication stops, organized activity ceases to exist, and individual uncoordinated activities return in an organization. So, organization in an organization is a virtual as the blood of life.

Job performance is the action as behavior relevant to organizational goals, Campbell (1999) which include both productive and counterproductive employee's behavior that contribute to as detract from set goals. It is the behaviour and outcomes that employee undertake that are contributed to organizational goals. This means job performance refers to the effectiveness and efficiency of individual behaviours.

Communication skills is the key to Health Records Officers motivation and performances i.e. it plays a vital role in the professionals' motivation and performance as real changes are taken place in Osun State Primary Healthcare Development Board which confront the new reality of lack of staff, increased workloads, longer hours and a greater emphasis on flexibility and performance. The act of communication

cannot be over-emphasized. It is the means by which people interact and work with one another, without communication skills the aims and goals of organized setting cannot be achieved. Communication skills are so important to success of Health Records Officers. However, it has been observed that there are still many Health Records Officers who find it difficult to communicate their thought, in that there is limit to their communication skills and they seem to have reached stumbling block in the process. They may sometimes struggle to convey their thoughts and ideas in an accurate manner, making it difficult to reach their full potential as a communicator hence hindered their performance. The main objective of this study is to assess the influence of communication skill on job performance of health records officers working in Osun State Primary Health Care Board. Its specific objectives include to: assess the influence of communication skill on Health Records Officers working in Osun State Primary Health Care Development Board; and know the factors hindering effective communication skills among the Health Records Officers working in Osun State Primary Healthcare Development Board.

2. METHODOLOGY

Research Design: This study adopted a cross-sectional study using in-depth interview with Health Records Officers. Structural focus group discussion guide were used to conduct Key Informant Interview (KII) and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The questions were pilot tested with the participant in some health facilities who did not participate in the final study. The structural interview guide developed contained questions to determine the respondent's demography, impression on influence, challenges and ways to enhance their job performance. The study population was sixty (60) Health Records Officers

working in Osun State Primary Healthcare Development Board.

Total enumeration was adopted because of the manageable size of the study population. The qualified Health Records officers who gave their informed consent were used to increase reliability. Data were collected using interview method which was done personally by the researchers. The questions were pre-structured to enhance focused discussion. The data collected include:

(i) Personal and social characteristic questions are drawn from the participating Health Records Officer. The questions include five (5) items that measure the personal and social characteristics of the participant such as age, sex, educational level, and work experience, category of staff and being interested in the Health Records Profession. The FGD consists of all cadres in the department.

(ii) The FGD was scheduled for the time convenient for participants by using the

time reserved for the department monthly meeting. Data were collected from the interview with the Head of the Departments in each health facilities on communication skills on job performance of their subordinates. In all five (5) focus group discussion with Health Records officers were conducted.

Method Of Data Analysis: The data extracted from the key informant interview (KII) and that of focus group discussion (FGD) were sorted and summarized with descriptive statistics.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis and Presentation of Data

This section discussed the data analysis and findings from the FGDs of Health Records officers working in Osun State Primary Health Care Development Board. The group consists of 60 Health Record Officers. The data were analyzed and the findings were discussed in accordance with the responses from the participants.

Table 1: Personal (Social-Demographic) Data

AGE-GROUPS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
21 – 30	10	16.7
31 – 40	24	40
41 – 50	20	33.3
50 and above	6	10
Total	60	100
GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Male	14	23.2
Female	46	76.7
Total	60	100
EDUCATIONAL LEVEL	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
NCE	6	10
HRT	18	30
HND	23	38.3
B.Sc.	9	15
Master's Degree	4	6.7
TOTAL	60	100

CATEGORY OF STAFF	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Health Record Assistants	6	10
Health Record Technicians	18	39
Health Record Technologists	23	38.3
Health Record Officers	13	27.7
Total	60	100
WORK EXPERIENCE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Less than 5 years	3	5
5 – 10 years	8	13.3
11 – 15 Years	22	36.7
16 – 20 years	17	28.3
More than 21 years	10	16.7
TOTAL	60	100

Age group: With the respect to age, the result shown in table 1 above shows that majority of the participants were in the 31 – 40 age group 24 (40%) followed by the 41 – 50 years of age group with 20 (33.3%) then 10 (16.7%) is the 21 - 30 years and the rest were over 50 years of age. The result indicates that the active age of HRO is the age between 31 – 40 years

Gender: The distribution of the participants by sex reveals that 14 (23.3%) were male and 46 (76.7%) were females. This indicates that a large proportion of the HRO that participated in the study were females.

Educational level: According to the result in Table 1 above, most of the participants 23 (38.3%) had Higher National Diploma followed by those 18 (30%) with Health Record Technician, 9 (15%) had B. Sc., 4 (6.7%) had Masters and the rest were National Certificate Holders. The table also

Table 2: Responses of Interviewees of key informants on communication among HRO

Communication	High	Moderate	Low	Total
Very effective	25	6	3	34
Effective	14	12	0	26
Non-Effective	0	0	0	0
Total	39	18	3	26

shows response rate for each stratum with the majority of the respondents 36 (60%) is Officer's cadres against 24 (40%) that were in sub officers' cadres.

Experience: most of the respondents 22 (36.7%) with more than 21 years' work experience and lastly 3 (5%) respondents with less than 5 years.

Level of communication among HRO

The result on table 2 above shows the response of interviewees of key information on effectiveness of communication among the Health Records officers working in Osun State Primary Health Care Development Board. Response from 39 participants indicates the communication was very effective, 18 moderate and 3 participants considered the communication to be low among HRO.

Influence of communication skills on their job performance

Table 3 shows thus: 100% (60) of respondents agreed that self-openness, positivism and empathy have high influence on job performance, clear expression of information, positive attitude in respecting others point of view enhance job performance. Majority of the respondents also considered social skill, idealized influence and inspiration, and intellectual stimulating as a communication skill that encourage and appreciate creative ideas, commitment to work and accepting new innovations which create friendly and conducive atmosphere for good job performance.

The result in Table 3 shows that effective communication skills have influence in job performance. This assertion can be confirmed by Ayatse (2005) in his study, observed that communication is needed to establish and disseminate the goals of the center price. This is because of the competencies and skills they possess will enable them to exhibit work behavior appropriate and relevant to the performance of job. Also the contextual theory affirms the above result through the contention of Pearce 1995, and Cronon 2000 that for communication skills to have influence on workers performance there is need for the message passed across to be properly understood by workers. It seeks to explicate how the creation and maintenance of social relation materialize in talk. Health Records Officers job performance in Osun State Primary Health Care Development Board depend significantly on communication skills.

DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to assess the influence of communication skills on job performance of Health Records Officers

working in Osun State Primary Health Care Development Board. In this study, the result indicates that the active age range of HRO is the ages between 31 – 40 years 24 (40%) while the large proportion of the respondents were female 46 (76%) in respect with distribution of educational qualification the result revealed that majority of the respondents had HRT and HND 51 (68.3%). The outcome of findings on category of staff indicates that majority of the respondents 36 (60%) were in officers' cadre.

It is noteworthy that effective communication system helps in achieving maximum productivity Tsai and Chuma (2009) observed "the sum total of an individual's satisfaction with information flow and relationship variables" has correlation with key variables such as job performance and turnover rates while suggests a link between communication and productivity as more complex than previously assumed. It is also believed that the mechanistic perspective is viewed as a technical system that allows information flow from one direction to another through the informative function of communication which is critical to provide recorded information to the officers so they can do their jobs in an effective and efficient manner. Therefore it can be seen from table 3 that good communication skills affects the level of HROs commitment corroborating based on this result, Arnold (2011) observed that the perception of people in communication process must be considered for what they think or feel affects considerably how they interact with the organizational environment.

Finally, results of the finding showed that communication skills increase job commitment, and elevate quality of services rendered by the HROs, this assertion can be

linked to Ayatse (2005) study which observed that communication skills are needed to establish and disseminate the targeted goals. This is because the competencies and skills they possess will enable them to exhibit work behaviours appropriate and relevant to the performance of job whilst (Brunette and Farr-Wharton 2004) findings suggest a strong relationship

between communication skills and effective job performance. Lack of communications skills constitutes one of the key obstacles to the productive performance of the team people. The findings indicate that the HROs needs strong communication skills bond where message will be conveyed effectively for the realization of stated goals, aims and objectives.

Table 3: Response of HRO on influence of communication skills on their job performance

S/N	Communication Skills		Job Performance							
			High		Moderate		Low		Total	
			N	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
1	Self-Openness	Clear expression of information	45	75	10	16.7	5	8.3	60	100
		Relaying information with ease	38	63.3	22	36.7	0	0	60	100
		Clarified expectational goals	55	91.7	5	8.3	0	0	60	100
2	Positivism	Positive attitude	39	65	18	30	3	5	60	100
		Encourage and appreciate each other	39	65	21	35	0	0	60	100
		HRO positive feelings towards subordinates	36	60	19	31.1	5	8.3	60	100
3	Empathy	Understand Emotions	45	75	15	25	0	0	60	100
		Respect others points of view	40	66.7	20	33.3	0	0	60	100
		Support of rights and dignitaries	45	75	15	25	0	0	60	100
4	Social Skills	Influence of behaviour	25	41.7	35	58.3	0	0	60	100
		Listening	48	80	12	20	0	0	60	100
5	Idealized Influence and Inspiration	Commitment	45	75	15	25	0	0	60	100
		Emulate positive behavior patterns	30	50	28	46.7	2	3.3	60	100
6	Intellectual stimulating	Encourage and appreciate creative ideas	46	76.7	14	23.3	0	0	60	100
		Accepting new innovations	50	83.3	10	16.7	0	0	60	100

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

SUMMARY: This study assessed the influence of communication skills on job performance of Health Records Officers working in Osun State Primary Healthcare Development Board. The study was a descriptive cross-sectional using focus group discussion guide to extract information from HROs working in Osun State Primary Health Care Development Board.

The result reveals that communication skills are adaptation skills that can motivate job stress. It is referred to behavior which can help individual express their feelings and needs well. Skilled communication is essential for Health Records Officer to maintain effective and sensitive relationship with patients, professional colleagues and other members of the health team i.e. good communication skill create mutual understanding which help in building genuine relationships while poor communication skills can affect job commitment and job performance of Health Record Officers. The study established that Health Record Officers goal attainment in Osun State Primary Health Care Development Board depends on communication skills.

4.2 CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study it has been considered that the human relationship, HROs job performance and professional goal attainment all depend on effective communication skills. That means that the job performance of Health Records Officers working in Osun State Primary Health Care Development Board depend on good and effective communication skills. Effective communication skills promote good human relationship among the HROs. It promotes the job performance and further leads to the attainment of Public Healthcare

Development Board goals. Thus ineffective/poor communication skills will lead to poor human relationship, ineffective job performance and poor attainment of goals.

The following recommendations have been made based on the findings of the study:

- i. Efforts should be made among the Health Records Officers to provide good communication guidelines to enable them to communicate effectively.
- ii. The Health Records Officers should develop good inter personal and organizational communication skills to communicate issues hindering the board objectives and those that are necessary to enable the Board reach its goals through.
- iii. Effective communication skills should be used as a tool to encourage HROs by communicating clearly, the aims and objectives as well as the expectation from every officer.

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